

Electrogenics

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents the information related to the Management system about Electronics Shop. This system is new in market for the reason of GST. We are adding GST for Products and generate the bill including GST. The system we described is fast and flexible for running each modules (window forms) and providing the information i.e. Reports of each products. By using this system, we can use the most flexible application for handling manual work in our software/system. This application saves the time which we are providing it to the user.

Keywords: *Window Forms, Data storage – My SQL*

Introduction

The Electro and Gym Management system is a Window-based application, in which we are providing a management that is going to be easily handled. In this project which we consider as this management system will support to end user to manage or utilize his manual paper work in the system. Mainly we are going to add some modules to this electro and gym management system which includes Invoice, Purchase details, Supplier Details, Products Details, etc. So the mentioned modules are the one which is going to be included in our system where the user can retrieve or store the information.

This system is useful when there is no software present in your computer and you want to run program at that time we simply use this system. It gives one system in that many modules (options) are present, user simply needs to select the options in which he/she is going to open the module. The database which we are going to use here is My SQL

where the database will contain the information regarding the system. We are using this information to store in the database in order to contain the information or data for the products and so on. User generate the any reports by searching the products, invoice, purchase details, customer name, etc

I. LITERATURE REVIEW

Electro and Gym management System

The main purpose of Electro and Gym Management System is to provide services to user's based on the knowledge of their work. Examples of these services include, online services which are provided to user's according to user's choice to create, load or store the information as well as choosing the platform (Modules) to run on or to create on, providing dynamic guidance services according to the users choice and storing it.

II. User-Friendly Electro and Gym Management System Based On User's demand

So it's not so surprising that there are now even some environments starting to emerge that you can run and develop from inside your system. These are system where you can edit information, run your application, and sometimes even instantly share your application for others to try. This is much more convenient than the typical process of downloading and installing a huge system such as any software or system.

The purpose and functionality of Electro and Gym management system application is A Window system can be accessed from a Operating System, such as Windows xp/7/8/10 or other OS. This system does not usually contain all of the same features as a traditional, or desktop although all of the basic

modules features, such as Any information, are typically present.

Timesaving IDE

This is an application that helps software people to coordinate their day-to-day activities with their demanding schedules/Management. For the everyday person who needs to run the system then there are often many work that need to be completed in a given day. Some of these works must be completed at a particular time, but others simply need to be completed when the user is at particular place. With the browser-based system, a user gets an advantage of saving the time and completing his work in less time.

Disadvantages of Existing System:

1. Billing Include GST: Maximum systems have not added GST for making Bill Including GST.

2. Difficult to send emails or sms without system: Many different system have not any email or sms facilities.

III. SCOPE AND OBJECTIVES

In this project we are going to make it easier for the user to run any mentioned modules on a single system.

The system provides a platform if the user doesn't have any of the knowledge than he/she has an option to operate or run it of the system through this window-based application.

This system provides us to store and retrieve information of any products and so on, We can create a new report and can load it into the pdf, excel or in doc format.

This criterion is very important to ensure that the proposed system gives less effort on user to load the Information or report and execute it.

The system in the project always will try to attract users by having all the facilities provided to them. One of the ways to attract user is by giving all the easy way around the System so that user can know about the creation of report or loading of existing report.

IV. WORK TO BE CARRIED OUT

Objective of this proposed system is to manage the information using which work can be managed in a friendly manner. The project uses windows form which enabled on any OS.

In this project which we consider as a system will support multiple options which are to each other in order to run any modules. Mainly we are going to add information about electro shop. This system saves the end users time from manual work. A user can Add, Update or Delete any information in the system and also generates any reports from the database.

The database which we are going to use here is MySQL where the database will contain the information regarding the customer, products, maintenance. We are using this information to store in the database in order to contain the information or data.

In the above diagram the actual work of the application is given. The admin login into that application by using the User-Id and password. The Admin has the authentication for accessing the database.

After the login process the home page is opened. The actual work of the admin is to maintain the information and reports..The admin's work is to store and retrieve the data to the database..

V. IMPLEMENTAION DETAILS WITH PROCEDURE

5.1. SNAPSHOTS OF PROJECT OUTPUT

Fig: Main

Fig:Customer Details

Fig: Maintenance

Fig: Invoice

Fig: Maintenance

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The project can just not be used for doing the Software, but also all the information related to that project whether it might be storing, retrieving and manipulating, etc. can be done too.

VII. REFERENCES

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